

Judul: Submission Acknowledgement

Tanggal: 2020-06-25 11:26

Pengirim: "Dr.Ayad F. Alkaim" <submissions@sysrevpharm.org>

Penerima: "Mr Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Mr Achmad Faqih:

Thank you for submitting the manuscript, "Relationship Of Farmers Characteristics To The Level Of Application Of Soybean Plant Technology (Glycine max L. Merrill)." to Systematic Review Pharmacy.

If you have any questions, please contact me. Thank you for considering this journal as a venue for your work.

Dr. Ayad F. Alkaim
Systematic Review in Pharmacy

Systematic Review in Pharmacy
<https://www.sysrevpharm.org/>

Judul: Systematic Review in Pharmacy. The paper was accepted for publication in Vol. 11 (8) 2020 with minor revisions.

Tanggal: 2020-07-20 09:10

Pengirim: "Dr.Ayad F. Alkaim" <submissions@sysrevpharm.org>

Penerima: "Mr Achmad Faqih" <achmad.faqih@ugj.ac.id>

Mr Achmad Faqih:

Three independent experts in the field have reviewed your manuscript. We are pleased to inform you that your paper was accepted for publication in Vol. 11 (8) 2020 on the condition of correcting minor revisions being made in response to the reviewers' comments given below.

You need to send the article, strictly formatted according to the template recommendations for authors, and correct the article on the reviewers' recommendations,

All revisions should be highlighted in the article in blue. We hope you will do great.

1. Please add the novelty of the results (1-2 sentences) in the abstract.
2. Please add 3-4 hypotheses of the study and show how they are tested in the results section.
3. Please write the source under each table, graphs, figures, and diagrams.
4. Authors should develop the conclusion. The authors should specify the main limitations of the study. Authors should explain better the academic contribution of the work developed. Highlighting what is innovative/original about the existing literature.
This paper is novel because The calculation confirms the new method effectiveness evaluation novelty of the article also consists of a conducted large-scale study describing the author's theoretical and practical prerequisites.
5. Also, Please elaborate on the novelty of your approach to Conceptual Strategic Quality Leadership (criteria, period, gender, etc.)

Deadline for corrections and payment: August 27, 2020.

* Please write in the subject of the email: revised article and payment foto.

Dr. Ayad F. Alkaim
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October 18th, 2020
SRP-December-2020

Dear Authors

Achmad Faqih

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We would like to inform you that your manuscript ID SRP-December has been accepted for publication in **SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS IN PHARMACY (ISSN 0975-8453)**. Your paper will be published in Volume 11 Issue 12 of 2020.

TITLE: RELATIONSHIP OF FARMERS CHARACTERISTICS WITH THE LEVEL OF APPLICATION OF SOYBEAN (*Glycine max L. Merrill*)

Thanks for submission of your work with us.

Regards,

Professor Dr. Lucius,

Associate Editor

SYSTEMATIC REVIEWS IN PHARMACY (ISSN 0975-8453)

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